

**PRINCIPLES AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF BUSINESS
COMMUNICATION****Kalandarova Safiya Tokhirovna**

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Аннотация: В статье освещены некоторые принципы и педагогические вопросы осуществления делового общения в многоплановых профессиональных ситуациях, а также усвоение речевых и поведенческие правила этикета и управление партнера

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, среда обучения, интегрирующее содержание, профильные предметы, мотивация, правила этикета, делового общения.

Abstract: The article highlights some principles and pedagogical issues in the implementation of business communication in multifaceted professional situations, as well as the assimilation of speech and behavioral rules of etiquette and partner management

Keywords: foreign language, learning environment, integrating content, profile subjects, motivation, rules of etiquette, business communication.

Taking into account the peculiarities of the development of the educational process, analyzing the educational situation in the system of technical universities, studying global trends in the development of professional training leads to the need to establish cause and effect relationships and dependencies that manifest themselves in the form of leading trends and principles of modern professional training for humanitarians in the light of the formation of a culture of foreign language in business communication. From the point of view of methodology, the concept of "trend" includes the possibility and potential of development, its direction and multivariance.

The trend reflects a certain order of a causal stable relationship between the components of the communication culture, in which changes in some components cause changes in others.

A heuristic role in determining the trends in the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication can be performed by the search for the main trend. To find such a trend, A.T. Nurmanov suggests, in particular, relying on a number of provisions: the leading trend should determine all othermore particular tendencies; set the overall structure; determine the techniques and methods of research.

Among the current trends in higher education in the humanities, one should first of all single out the tendency to focus on the cultural development of the individual. We have already traced the connection of the general culture with the culture of communication and the culture of business communication within the framework of the specialist's professional competence. In this regard, within the framework of this trend, there is a need to create a single educational multicultural space, by which we mean a set of ideal educational environments that carry specific value content. Such cultural environments are a stable set of material and personal elements with which the social subject interacts and which influences his activities, spiritual needs, interests and value orientations. The creation of a single multicultural educational space in higher education in the humanities actualizes the development of the personality of a future specialist in the humanities in relation to the experience of culturally appropriate behavior and activities. The effective functioning of a single multicultural educational space of the university and its contribution to the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication in the system of higher humanitarian education is determined by the following factors:

- development and implementation of interactive educational technologies for the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication; support of attitudes towards general cultural development and selfdevelopment;
- orientation of educational activities towards cultural goals.

The formation of a multicultural educational space in the system of higher education in the humanities is realized through the values presented in the following logic:

- personal meanings of education and professional activity;
- teacher-student dialogue as a dialogue of cultures;
- participation in cultural-creating activities as an indispensable individual

experience of the individual. The second trend is closely related to the first one: the tendency of axiologisation of education, based on the perception and appropriation of values that arise when a person is focused on understanding, updating, mastering the values of human culture and the professional activity of an individual. This is due to the perception of the teacher's personality as a value of social development, and the personality of each person as unique, unlike others. Value orientation performs the function of an internal stimulus and guideline for the behavior of both the teacher and students. The stimuli of human activity are further developed: the need is transformed into interests, and interests are transformed into values. The changing needs of modern society and the development of educational processes serve as a guideline for changing/reassessing values. The principle of scientific character means that in the process of forming a culture of foreign language business communication of students in the system of higher humanities education, modern scientific achievements in the field of pedagogy, psychology, methods of teaching foreign languages should be used, which directly affects the quality of the developed technologies, reduces the costs of their creation and implementation.

The subjective perception and appropriation of cultural values by teachers and students is determined by the wealth of the individual, his professional self-awareness, which plays an important role in the search for ways to update the content of higher education in the humanities. The formation of a motivational-value attitude to future professional activity is of fundamental importance: by engaging in activity, a person forms a professional environment, carrying out an individual creative rethinking of tasks, content, forms and types of activity. The third important trend in the formation

of a culture of foreign language business communication is the dependence of the formation of the subject position of the future specialist on the degree of his own activity. Since the subjective development of a personality is based on the individual's own activity, it is necessary for the culture of foreign language business communication to:

- availability of conditions conducive to the manifestation of the internal potential of the student;

- orientation to the personality of a student who is aware of his professional choice and responsibility for it;

- the need for independent movement in the direction of multi-vector mastery of the culture of foreign language business communication. These trends find their practical expression in the implementation of the principles of forming a culture of foreign language business communication. **Zagvyazinsky** interprets the principle as “an instrumental expression of the pedagogical concept given in the categories of activity, a methodological expression of the learned laws and patterns, knowledge about the goals, essence, structure of learning, expressed in a form that allows them to be used as regulatory norms of practice”. The principle of integrity means that the internal unity of the system of forming a culture of foreign language business communication of students of higher humanitarian education by means of interactive educational technologies should be achieved as a result of the interaction of its elements. An integrative feature of this system is the harmonization of all its structural components. In accordance with this principle, a single content of the system for the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication of humanities students is constructed, reflecting the natural, objective unity of strategic, tactical and operational goals. The principle of dialogization, based on the equality of the positions of communication partners, the acceptance of the interlocutor into one's inner world as a value, is one of the basic principles for the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication. Firstly, the idea of dialogue is connected with the personality, the formation of its "I", the awareness of ways of interacting with another "I" and the

complementarity of positions. Secondly, the idea of dialogue requires such interaction between the subjects of education, as a result of which conditions will be created for the formation and development of the individual with his unique perception of the world and understanding of the ways of interacting with others. Thirdly, the essence of dialogic techniques is to address the personality, develop and enrich its experience. There is a reorientation from the assimilation of knowledge received from outside, to the need to use reasoning, analysis, interpretation, to express personal judgment. The dialogical approach in modeling a subject within the framework of interactive learning technologies provides the indisputable priority of the subject-subject relationship between the teacher and students, when the teacher encourages students to general and professional development and creative self-realization. The principle of individualization is implemented in the sense that it is based on the relationship between the freedom of choice and the student's personal responsibility for the results of their activities. It is important to connect educational information with the life experience of students, to develop cognitive motives and curiosity. The effectiveness of the implementation of this principle is ensured by the educational environment based on constructive communication and critical reflection on the value of information. An important role is given to identifying key questions, as opposed to simply answering the teacher's questions. Since creativity serves the principles of high-level subjective development of the individual, the content of this principle lies in creating conditions for the active formation of creative abilities and choosing effective ways of self-realization for each student, applying active and creative methods, systematic work in shaping the culture of business communication in a foreign language, including knowledge from other fields, and focusing on activating students' thinking. The principle of motivating stimulation plays a role in the stability of motivation: the content of the educational material, the organization of educational activities, the style of the teacher's pedagogical activities, competence in collective forms of activity, and evaluating students' academic performance in comparative dynamics. It is necessary to put students in a situation of independent goal-setting, ensure that students see the

connection between their efforts and task completion, make the lesson more engaging through original and visual materials, and clearly structure the material to facilitate perception.

The principle of involving each student in group work. To achieve this, it is necessary to model activities in such a way that the group's results depend on the contribution of each student. The atmosphere of novelty and comfort in the workplace, creating a favorable atmosphere permeated with confidence, conscious discipline, enthusiasm, and emotional activity, plays an important role in preparing for the creation of a business intercultural community. Such mutual understanding can be created through special stimulating techniques, games, taking into account socio-personal factors, and situational behavior orientation. The principle of participation of each student in the group organization of work. To do this, it is necessary to model the activity in such a way that the results of the group depend on the contribution of each student. An important role in preparing for the creation of a business intercultural community is played by the atmosphere of novelty and a sense of comfort in the workplace, creating a favorable atmosphere, imbued with confidence, conscious discipline, passion, passion and emotional activity. Such mutual understanding can be created with the help of special stimulating techniques, games, taking into account social and personal factors, situational orientation of behavior.

The principle of independence. In accordance with this principle, the function of the teacher moves to the organizational and advisory plane, provided that all the skills and abilities of students must be formed in the classroom. The teacher organizes an educational environment where the student, relying on his personal potential, determines the ways of his activity, the ways of self-realization, taking into account his interests. This principle echoes the idea of student autonomy, which H. Barkowski and H. Funk define as the ability to responsibly manage their learning activities. The organization of classroom and independent work provides a high level of personal responsibility of the student for the results of educational work, while at the same time providing the possibility of independent choice of the sequence and depth of study of

the material, compliance with reporting deadlines, etc. The introduction of a point-rating system of control is called upon to play a special role in raising the level of educational independence. Consistent orientation towards the independence of students in the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication is expressed in the following: awareness of the goals, objectives and content of teaching a foreign language of business intercultural communication;

- conscious and systematic development of language and speech educational material;
 - participation in the choice of types of work with educational material;
 - development of skills for perception and analysis of authentic language texts and development of receptive and productive strategies for working with them;
 - formation of skills of critical thinking, argumentation, search for ways to independently solve a communicative or research problem;
 - independent search for additional information;
- The principle of clear explication of goals. All these provisions are reflected in Figure, which presents the developed structural model for the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication of students in the system of higher education in the humanities. Structural model of the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication of students in the system of higher education in the humanities

Components of competence		
Linguistic	intercultural	Communicative
<p>Purpose: for mation of a culture of foreign language business communication of students in the system of higher humanitarian education</p>		

Personal and businessTechnologies	point-rating system	problem learning method
case analysis method	role play method	business game method
personality-oriented tasks	drafting projects	regional commentary method

Conclusions. Among the main trends in the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication of students in the system of higher humanities education, the following are distinguished: orientation towards the cultural development of the individual, axiologisation, dependence of the formation of the subject position of the future specialist on the degree of his own activity.

From these trends follow the principles of forming a culture of foreign language business communication of students in the system of higher education in the humanities: the principle of scientific character, the principle of integrity, the principle of dialogization,

Trends:

- orientation to the cultural development of the individual
 - axiologisation of education
 - dependence of the formation of the subject position of the future specialist on the degree of his own activity
- psychological and pedagogical conditions for the formation of a culture of foreign language business communication of students in the system of higher humanitarian education are: scientifically based organization of the process of forming a culture of foreign language business communication; updating the subjective positions of the student and teacher in the process of forming a culture of foreign language business communication; creation of a culturally appropriate development environment; stimulation of students' motivation to receive a personally

significant educational product; monitoring, the subject of which is the level of formation of the culture of foreign language business communication of students.

Identification of the leading trends, principles and psychological and pedagogical conditions that ensure the effective formation of a culture of foreign language business communication of students in the system of higher humanities education, allows not only to establish patterns and mechanisms for achieving productive results, but also to outline ways for further development.

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